

[XXX] Interview - [XXX] ProjectKey:

I: Interviewer
R: Respondent

[Transcriber's comment – quite a few unclears due to poor quality audio]

I: Okay, so I have just turned it on, thank you very much to consenting to have a quick interview with me. So what we're going to do today is just explore [XXX] in terms of its origins, we'll explore some lessons you have learned via engaging in [XXX] and perhaps your thoughts as to how we can use those lessons in creating a network of responsible research moving forward. So in the first instance I just wondered if you could speak to the origins of [XXX], how did it come about, what was the rationale for actually having [XXX] as a project?

R: Yes, so [XXX] was basically one of the projects funded by European funding, [XXX], which stands for platforms for collecting [XXX] and [XXX] innovation, and [XXX] was basically the first project that I am aware that was funded to develop a toolkit of collecting intelligent platforms that could help civic society organisation and basically have more effective, productive (unclear 0.01.36) discussions, decision-making processes by using and leveraging the knowledge of their network. Sorry? Do you have a -

I: [overspeaking] Sorry, no I was just listening, sorry about that.

R: So this project was basically proposed by an existing network of researchers who have been working on this for many years. We have been working on this for many years before, and when we came across this (unclear 0.02.15) we thought that they were targeted to the application of the technology that we were developing and we were starting a design. So we were really a group of technology designers and researchers that have the (unclear 0.02.35-0.02.37) technology that can impact society in a positive way. So we are coming up with a local network in civic society organisation to write this project and I think that was something that made the project quite special because yes we were researchers but we were applied researchers and we partnered up with (unclear 0.03.10) organisation. And the way we approached even the writing up of the project was (unclear 0.03.15), so even before writing it we consulted our community partners, asking what are the main points of their network that made their life difficult. So we built the project really on real (unclear 0.03.34-0.03.37) and on the basis of that we drew the project and we brought guidelines of the platform that we wanted to design (unclear 0.03.49). So basically the whole project was all about designing, developing and testing these technologies with this group of people.

I: Okay, and what was your role within [XXX]? What exactly was your role within the project?

R: I was the scientific coordinator of the project, but at the same time I was also one of the main technical partners. So my university designed inside the project and developed and then released at the end of the project three open source collective intelligence tools. I had this double role.

I: Right. How long were you on the project for?

R: The project was two years, so (unclear 0.04.48-0.05.00) interesting. It was very hard. In two years we had co-designed, implemented and tested with 15 organisations seven technologies that we had developed inside the (unclear 0.05.20), so within two years. Actually that's why it was also mentioned as one of the most successful (unclear 0.05.30-0.05.33), I think last year (unclear 0.05.38) was really a fantastic experience (unclear 0.05.43-0.05.45).

I: **Oh fantastic. So you mentioned you had about 15 organisations working on the [XXX] project at the time that you did the project. So I wondered in terms of the working relationship that you had with these organisations, was it one where you engaged with them on a regular basis? If that was the case, was it meeting up annually or monthly? How did the working relationship pan out?**

R: In our specific process, engagement was the main issue, the main task of the project, so after we developed and even before we developed the tool. We had three organisations inside but they were not enough for testing all the tools. So what we did is we set inside the proposal two open calls for community partners that were tackling the key problem that our technology helped to solve and they wanted to engage in testing them. So we would launch this call, we launched this open call I think twice, no once I think. I don't remember if it was once or twice, along the two years. So we set up a website, we disseminated, then there was a deadline, there was some procedural evaluation. We received, I think, about 30 applications and then we assessed them and we selected 15 winners. And then we allocated money for the different organisations who engaged. I think the biggest organisation, they could bid for money, they could say 'Testing this with my organisation, this use case, I need £10,000' or 'I need £25,000' or 'I need £1000' or 'I need £2000.' So they could bid for different quantities of money and then we would assess whom to give the money to.

I think we had in total a £50,000 budget and we funded 15 organisations to engage with our technology. The biggest amount was given to [XXX], I think, network, and they got £25,000 because they engaged over 200 people into an online discussion with one of our technologies, so it was a (unclear 0.08.35). And then the other £25,000 we split between other organisations basically.

I: **Alright, okay. So in terms of the engagement with individuals in different organisations, did you find that having some sort of personal relationship -**

R: What, sorry?

I: **Having a personal relationship or personal ties with key members of the different organisations -**

R: Sorry, (unclear 0.09.02-0.09.04). What?

I: **So I was trying to enquire into the role of personal ties, so personal relationships with individuals in the different organisations.**

[phone call ends] [resumes]

I: **Hello?**

R: Hello?

I: Sorry about that, I'm not sure why the line went dead. Hello? Can you hear me now? Is it clearer?

R: Yes, I can hear you. Can you hear me well?

I: Yes, I can hear you as well. So I said I was trying to enquire as to the role of personal ties, so personal relationships that you had with individuals in different organisations, the individuals that were bidding for the money. Did you find that having some personal ties with them facilitated their engagement with the [XXX] project?

R: Absolutely. Well it was a bit of a mix in the sense that personal relationships were absolutely key but they entered at different stages. So first of all, they were important because in the dissemination of the open of course each of the [XXX] members reached out to their network, so it was a snowball effect. So the people that ended up even knowing about the call were already part of our personal network, and some of the people that we invited we directly knew already from previous work and over conferences and stuff, so this was one. And then even in the cases in which we received submissions from people that nobody knew actually in the consortium, it became very important to develop a personal relationship. So before we even started organising the testing, we had several informal meetings, (unclear 0.11.35) calls, we got to know each other, we got to understand better the problems of each organisation. Then we got to explain to them about our vision for the tools, so there was a lot of dialogue and personal relationship building going on, even before the real work started. And that was quite important for the development of the whole project and I would venture to say that the most successful use cases were the ones that were built on the strongest or oldest relationships. So it was definitely an important factor.

I: Okay. Initially when you were introducing the project you talked about the context in which [XXX] emerged as a project, but I wondered if you could speak to things like the funding climate at the time, the political climate at the time. Were there any particular drivers which actually created the context for [XXX] as a project to emerge? I'm trying to enquire as to whether there were particular issues around the time when the project was initiated that stimulated the mood for [XXX] as a project.

R: It's a very good question. I think [XXX] was funded because there was finally and interestingly a very positive and innovative political interest into developing collective platforms to improve society, which was not really very – especially in the IT grand funding – present before [XXX], these collective awareness platforms for social innovation, calls were launched. So definitely there was a very positive and serendipitous meeting between this political interest in the EU to work in developing technologies for good and then what our research network had been doing for years. Without that political interest [XXX] would have never been funded [laughs], so I think that political interest is very important.

Funnily enough though, it has been discontinued because [XXX] has now disappeared. There has been, surprisingly, because we have built such a big community that even the researchers have created such a strong network of collaborators... When the (unclear 0.15.22) launched, the message that this funding grant had to be discontinued, we tried to affect the political interest and will by gathering some signatures, so I think 100 different organisations and research (unclear 0.15.45) claiming the importance of this research grant and trying to affect the political decision not to discontinue it. We didn't get anywhere, so it was (unclear

0.15.59). So at the moment it doesn't exist anymore. Even though interestingly enough there are still meetings going on [laughs]. It's like if the funding has disappeared then the network has just survived, so there are still meetings about the [XXX] network. The last meeting was actually two months ago I think, so there are still a lot of researchers interested in this topic. But at the moment (unclear 0.16.33-0.16.39) there is not a place for that anymore.

I: Okay, and when the project was ongoing, because clearly there were a lot of collaborators on the project, can you quickly just speak to what the roles of these collaborators were? Was it that they were in charge of particular objectives? How did it work? How did you pull it all together? Because clearly you had multiple collaborators working on the project, so how did you link their contribution to the objectives of the project?

R: In terms of operationally, we were all very distributed so we were working each one in its own university but we had very regular meetings. Also because the relationship with the community partners and the integration of the different technologies required in some cases daily interchanges of communication. So we were really working at distance, but very intensively talking a lot on Skype. We actually were using Google Hangouts a lot at the time and of course different forms of sharing documents, Google Drive and stuff like that. The usual stuff, I would say, for project management.

I: So in terms of how you worked together, in terms of the structure of working, it was mostly remotely. Is that correct?

R: It was mostly remote, even with the partners, testing the platforms. So even when we had to give some training of how to use the tools, it was told at distance. We only met I think twice a year between the various project meetings and the events of the European Commission (unclear 0.19.01) and stuff like that. Probably we met two, three times a year. So we didn't meet face to face that often.

I: So how did working with this structure develop over the course of the two years? How did working remotely develop? Did it progress nicely? What kind of barriers did you encounter?

R: The main problem we had, as I told you before... The initial stages were fine because they were very intense technology development phases. We had to design, code the tools and test it and pre-test it, so that was almost like each organisation worked in isolation. So up to that stage it was fine. The problem started when we had to engage with the other partners outside the project, and we had to convince them to try and use our technologies, and that was a very hard part because the most difficult part is that we wanted to do realised experiments with real organisations, with real problems. But we were a research project, so we needed to do science in a real life context, and this presents a very big challenge because we had requirements of time or numbers of attendees or the fact that some attendees present at one test should be present at the second two otherwise all the sample was useless.

And all these things, you can plan them from the research side but it can go very wrong when you test it with real people because people drop out, they have personal needs. So they may say yes and then they don't do things and then gathering attendance is very complicated and we follow very weird rules. So sometimes we were doing some (unclear 0.21.42) social media dissemination of some of our testing events because some of these events were live challenges, happening from this day to this day. And we massively spent a lot of energy to disseminate this and gather

participants and then very few people would show up, and then you would have the opposite at other events where you have not disseminated at all but then three times the number of people shows up. [laughter]

Actually, I don't know if you happened to read our final report of the project?

I: Yes.

R: But in the final report of the project we worked all together with all the team members, the community partners, all the people. We started to reflect on the problems and the hard part in engaging in realised experiments, so we have provided a list of a lot of reflections that could be interesting for you, the hard, open questions that we didn't solve in [XXX]. We just [laughs] realised that engagement is the hardest part and a lot of the time we had to (unclear 0.23.18) our plan, so we thought we would be able to engage thousands of people and then we ended up engaging hundreds in the best cases. So scale is a real problem.

I: So if you were going to identify one major problem that the challenge faced, what would you say would be the biggest challenge from that list that were identified by individuals? Which one challenge would you say was the biggest challenge that the [XXX] project encountered?

R: I think that was it. The biggest challenge was technology engagement, so getting people in their busy lives to get the time and the motivation to try something new or something different to solve their problems.

I: And what would you say would be the biggest advantage of using the model that you used? Because clearly people, individuals were working remotely and there was some contact in person but it wasn't the usual mode of working. What would you say would be the biggest advantage of that?

R: Sorry, I didn't get the question. What was the usual way of working? Of who? Of the partners we wanted to engage with or on our team?

I: Of members of the team, the individuals within different universities. Because you said individuals worked in individual units, in the first stage they worked remotely and electronically as well. What would you say was the biggest advantage of working in that way for the [XXX] project?

R: I'm not sure there was an advantage. We didn't have an alternative. So we did the best we could with the fact that we were distributed across different spaces, so some of them were in the US and Canada so we really could not... But of course [laughs] we could have met more often face to face, it would have been better. I really don't think that the success of [XXX] was behind our project management procedure at all. I don't think that was the key success factor. We didn't do anything special compared to other projects, we used very standard tools in the standard way, so I don't think it was about managing procedures or roles or sequence of activities.

It was more a matter of motivation and having a small group, because we were not a huge group, of people really motivated and who had a shared goal and a common vision and somehow, in a very (unclear 0.27.01) way of collaborating we managed to produce and achieve a lot. But it was really not about the tools we used and how we divided the work. It was I think more about this common vision and the fact that we were going all in the same direction which is not what usually happens in new projects. You have ten partners and each one is trying to achieve different things from the same project and they think they don't usually overlap. So you have a

bundle of people trying to organise themselves but each one going a different way, and that's quite [laughs] complicated.

I think the success was that even though we had different tools, different research agendas, we had the same pragmatic goal, so it was not about the research goal being the same, it was the pragmatic goal. What we wanted to achieve was the same thing pragmatically and the vision was the same, though the technology was different, the research area was different. But the pragmatic goal and the high-end level vision, the values driving us, were exactly the same. So I think that was why it worked well. It really was not about how we [laughs] organised ourselves. Actually we were not that good at that, if you want to ask. [laughs] I don't think we were the best. I have seen other projects in which there was much better project management than in our case, I think.

I think one thing that was really good and is probably relevant was we had a very, very good dissemination partner which was not involved at all in our activities, but did a great job in telling our story to the rest of the world in a way that was interesting and understandable. So I think that was successful. We had a very, very good dissemination partner who did an amazing job of all media communication work. And they were so amazing that they were not bothering the researchers that much. [laughs] I think they were amazing. If I had to say, I think part of our success was also that. So there was this combination of freedom for the researchers, alignment of intent and then very skilful media communication.

I: When you say skilful media communication and dissemination, can you shed some light on that? Was it the fact that they were disseminating to the circles that you'd normally expect to reach or they were submitting much, much more widely? What made their strategy extremely successful?

R: Look, they were professional, really. They were good at different things, not only at where to spread the media but also how to create the media thread. So they would just know how to tell stories that are engaging, understandable, easy, and then they would know how and to whom these stories should be sent. So I wouldn't know what their (unclear 0.31.18) was because you should talk to them [laughs]. That was when I realised that this is really a profession. It's not something that researchers know how to do [laughs], because it is really something different. And they would (unclear 0.31.41) just interviewers and then create video clips of promotional videos or they could ask us very simple details describing our research, but they would make it into beautiful posters and flyers. They would have some different ways, they would have monthly (unclear 0.32.11) news that they would send to specific networks. They would be very (unclear 0.32.21) in the way they would monitor everything we were doing. Everything we would do they would create social media presence for it. Any physical event would be accompanied by some digital presence, YouTube channel. They had a very big mix of reach (unclear 0.32.53) to create this media presence. So I think they were really good and I think that made a big difference. Because we did excellent jobs but if they didn't do that probably nobody would have known. [laughs]

I: Alright, that's good. So initially before you talked about how good the dissemination strategy was you quickly made some reference to gender, and I wondered if you could speak to how gender was addressed within the [XXX] project, issues around diversity and gender? Were they recognised in the project -

R: [overspeaking] Okay, now I'm going to tell you something that I want anonymised. Is that possible?

I: Yes, our entire narrative is going to be anonymised, of course.

R: Okay, if you can stop the recording now I'm going to tell you personally something which actually was one of the key factors (unclear 0.33.54). [laughs] But you can't write that anywhere, so please stop recording and don't analyse this data.

I: Okay, so if I stop this now then we can start later -

R: [overspeaking] Yes.

I: Okay, I'll just stop this now.

[recording paused and restarted]

I: Okay, so I'm just going to ask you a few questions around the membership of [XXX]. I know you've talked about the different universities that engaged and the different collaborators, but do you know if there were any requirements that helped you identify who the collaborators would be?

R: No. We did not, and this was one of the lessons learned. We did not and that was a mistake and we realised at the end of the project. So the way we decided what our community partners for the network would be was really on the basis of who knows what. So people, organisations that we have heard about or that we know that are famous, we would go online, we would look for people, we would contact them, so really on the basis of visibility and reputation. Then we realised that was wrong. And another indicator that (unclear 0.35.41) visibility was size, network size. So because we wanted to reach thousands of people we tried to select networks that were saying online that they have hundreds of thousands of participants. Then we realised that 99% of the cases... When an organisation told us 'We have 3000 participants or users' they didn't have much more than a mailing list. So they just had 3000 email addresses, these were not real networks. So we would expect them to engage these people in some proactive way while these organisations just had emails. They don't have any direct way to contact these people, they didn't know them, they didn't know much about their interests, what their problems were – really, very little more than a bunch of email addresses.

So we realised that if we had to write [XXX] again, we would ask and our criteria would be completely different. So instead of asking for numbers of attendees, we would rather try to identify organisations that are really in tune with the research and active research and applied research work, and not all organisations have this mindset. So (unclear 0.37.42) the organisations that like trying things that go wrong, that like innovation, they like playing and high-risk, high-reward things, they have to be maybe smaller but very committed, a very strongly-tied network of participants that share a common goal and the common value behind the project. And numbers don't really matter.

So it matters much more what they are up to doing with us and that they would do it with us with the same goal as us. So we would probably interview them instead of just sending an email. We would try and figure out if the people leading this network have the same mindset, we would try to understand what problems they are having, whether they are really aligning with the problems we are trying to solve. We would try to understand if they are testing at all what are their expectations? Are they expecting a fully functioning tool or are they okay with research and development or engaging with research and development? We don't know the problems that this can

have. So we will just do it in a completely different way. I'm not sure if this answers your question but this how -

I: Yes, it does. But the other thing that actually springs to mind from your reply is I just wondered... So these organisations, why did they even choose to engage with [XXX]? Because clearly there was a rationale for [XXX] wanting to involve them. What was the need for them to join [XXX] or to collaborate with [XXX]?

R: Well, first of all they wanted to collaborate because the main goal is to provide tools, (unclear 0.40.06) technologies for large-scale discussion. So all these communities recognised that they needed that and they would like to test the new technology so that's why they needed us, because they are like 'Oh yes this is exactly what my organisation needs, so I want to be involved.' The statement of the problem, they were buying into that. And then when they got to do it, then you realised that the expectation that many people have of using your tools are completely not in line with the research and innovation, because they are just expecting tools that are products, they are beautiful, well-designed, (unclear 0.41.03), they work well, they have a million features.

So then they would soon go back to their own tools, because this tool would be perhaps not as good as they wanted or too difficult to learn or it was not really embedded into the practice of other people that they were working with. So getting to use them in practice was too complicated. And these are people that were trying to use it in their real life, so they had deadlines, they had things they had to achieve or do for their organisation, so at some point it was not their fault because they had to say 'I'm sorry, I didn't manage to do this, I have to go back and do things using' – whatever, Facebook. So that was the issue.

That's why one of the main lessons learned from [XXX] is that you cannot do real-life experiments and real-life research in action unless you have organisations that know what research is, and with all the intersection of research, the fact that things go wrong and you learn by doing and you try one thing and then you fix it. [laughs] And this is not something that all organisations have either the will or the time or the predisposition to do. Even when (unclear 0.43.00) in their manifesto. So what we have discovered is despite what is written on a random webpage, when we got to know the people we realised that there were very few organisations that were really sharing the research and development and innovation culture. It's literally a culture. And it's not something that you can either impose or learn. Well no, I'm sure you can learn it if you want to but you can't impose it on an organisation if that organisation has a different drive. So I think it's an important (unclear 0.43.48) for people who want to do real-life experimentation in applied research.

I: Okay, I'm going to quickly try and explore... Because I know before the interview started you spent some time explaining to me that [XXX] is not a network or a project that has come undone. I would just like to quickly explore the funding model and the governance structure. I recognise that there might be bits, there might be questions that you don't know the answer to and if that's the case then I'm happy for you to just say 'This was not applicable to [XXX]' and we'll just move on.

So in the first instance I know you said [XXX] was funded by a grant. Is that right?

R: Yes.

I: Okay, so can you speak to some of the managerial issues in particular? Things like governance and the management structure of [XXX]. How was it structured in terms of management?

R: I don't know. I think I don't remember. [laughs] I don't remember and I think it was a general static project management structure, so we had project coordinators, then we had (unclear 0.45.15) committee and then I think we had an advisory board even, and then project leaders and that's it. And then our project leader had to respond for the scientific part, to the scientific coordinator and for the deliverables for the project coordinator and that's it, really. But in reality we were all the same ten people with different roles and we were doing it in a very fluid way. Decisions were usually made in plenary Skype meetings, with everyone present, so it was very fluid. We were not that many people.

I: Okay, so in terms of the funding for [XXX], besides the research fund, were there any other sources of funding?

R: Each partner university was already bringing its own resources. And actually now we are maintaining the technology on our university resources, because this technology we developed, it is still in use, and we maintain it just at the expense of our university because we want to carry on research and we believe in the impact it has on society. So it really has had a life of its own. And also the company that developed the tools are still working with them so I think they have sought new grants for developing them further. I have a new grant now (unclear 0.47.08-0.47.11) and I will develop it further. So it has required a mix of funding in order to stay alive after the end of the project. And the funding was coming both from the (unclear 0.47.27) university attending or the new customers that the companies could have or new grants that the PI in the project was able to attract.

I: Alright, so funding was a very important part of the project. Is that correct?

R: Sorry?

I: Having the funds actually was a very important part of having the project -

R: Having what? Having the...?

I: Having the funding in place was a very big part of the project actually starting and being completed. Would you say that was the case?

R: Of course having the funding... Without the initial funding the project would not have existed. That's absolutely true. But without the personal funds of the participants, the outcomes of the project would be dead by now. So I would say that the identification of personal finance was really key or follow-on funding was very key for the sustainability of the project result and it is actually the key to delivering impact because at the end of the project we had lots of (unclear 0.49.02) to develop. We tried, we (unclear 0.49.05) community. I don't know about the other seven tools, but only on one of my tools do we now have thousands of users. So we have way beyond in different organisations, ten different countries, using different sectors, learning, education... So if we didn't have that follow-on funding this project would never have had an impact. It would have just (unclear 0.49.40) [laughs] so even if the initial funding from the EU was absolutely important, equally important was the follow-on funding, otherwise this technology would be lost.

I: So did the project had an annual budget in the first year and the second year? Did it explicitly have a budget to guide the activities for, say, the first year and the second year?

R: Yes. The project had two years and for each year we had a budget.

I: So regarding communication, I know you talked about having the remote communication and things like that, but did you have management meetings as well? And how frequent were these to manage the direction of the project?

R: No. We didn't have management meetings. All the direction of the project was decided in a plenary during our project meetings and all the partners and all the people would be present, not only the people in the management team, all the project team.

I: And how did you monitor the effectiveness of the project? How was it measured, say, at three months, at six months, at one year? Was it measured and if it was how was it measured?

R: I don't know, because at that time these measures were the things that this company, this (unclear 0.51.18) with media and dissemination, they were really good at doing, all the tracking, all the engagement, visibility statistics, all the social presence and all these metrics. So I don't know exactly. I think we had the usual...Of course we were developing tools so some metrics were how many users you had, how many communities you engage, your (unclear 0.51.51) and how many papers of course you produce, how many presentations at conferences you gave, how many workshops you organised – there were lots of the usual metrics of research and engagement success I think at the time.

I: I know it's ended, I keep going back to the fact that it's ended, but does the project have some sort of action plan? At the time it was ending did it have some sort of project plan in terms of things like a five-year roadmap or even a (unclear 0.52.29) of things that potentially the project would still be achieving post the project?

R: No, we didn't do it and with some of the partners we lost trust, also because of personal circumstances of some of the people. So the company closed down, this dissemination company, at the same time I went on maternity leave straight away at the end of the project, so I was away from work for two years, so we never brought a [XXX]2, we never even sought funding for [XXX]2 because the core team [laughs] was not available. So we lost touch for a couple of years. So that's why we didn't have a plan, we didn't create a plan, we didn't follow a plan.

The interesting thing is that technology survives a few months [laughs] in the sense that because we disappeared but our tools keep existing and our media presence keeps existing, then things kept happening. I constantly receive requests from people who want to use our tools. I am writing (unclear 0.54.03) my university about [XXX] tools. The new funding that I have attracted now from the US Navy, they are related to [XXX]. So I have to say even though we did not have a plan and we had special circumstances for two years, a few people had to stop working on [XXX], the fact that we had a digital mark and that our technology stayed alive for people to use made the difference so that the concept goal is still alive, even though the project has ended. And we didn't have any follow on plan.

I: [overspeaking] Was there ever a risk and mitigation plan? Was there ever any plan to counter risk and mitigate against risk? Did [XXX] ever have a risk and mitigation plan in place?

R: We did. And I think we acted upon it because one of the risks we identified while writing the project was about engagement and to mitigate that we created the open call, and in fact we used it because the internal engagement with the partners inside the project didn't work out. One of the partners had to, again for personal circumstances, drop out, the community partner, so it was very important that we had inside the project organised and planned some funding resources for the open call so that we could recruit new networks and new organisations to work with. And we had the proper funding to do that, because a lot of people would have not participated in the open challenge if there was not funding concentrated on that. So it was quite important that we had allocated enough money for engagement and for the open call in the project.

I: I know you talked about Google Hangouts, working remotely, but how was information circulated among members of the consortium?

R: Mostly email.

I: And what would you say were the general issues which would have affected governance of [XXX]? So not the management per se but more of the governance side of things.

R: You mean governance of what? Money? Data? Communication? What time of governance?

I: In terms of things like the working of the management board or even the plenary when you had the plenary, things like that. What kind of challenges did you encounter and how did you resolve those?

R: Well like in all very bottom up organisations the challenge was that a lot of the time we disagreed and had very [laughs] long, long, long discussions. So there was a challenge of agreeing on a certain line of action. But as I said, sometimes we disagree and of course there was no way to reach an agreement, but most of the time, because we were a small group of reasonable people who knew each other, had a very high opinion of each other, we tended to find a compromise. So there weren't fights inside the project.

Now that you say that, the only problem (unclear 0.58.30) incurred was between some of the partners with the project coordinator, but in terms of how the money was managed. There was a problem of money management, that was one (unclear 0.58.46-0.58.47), because we had a project coordinator that was not in the spirit of the project. So he was quite bogged down in the allocation of the money and sometimes did not ascribe to the group, so he would say 'Okay you don't get this money' or 'You get this money' [laughs] or 'You don't do that' and that was a problem with some of the partners. That was a bit bad. But there was nothing we could do about that because it was mostly for how we had set up the management of the funds for travel, conferences, and this was all in the hands of the project coordinator and it didn't go to the single partners. So the project coordinator sometimes was quite peculiar in the way they decided not to give money to some partners [laughs] and the partners were pissed off. So I think that was a little issue at some point. That's the only thing.

I: Were there any other challenges encountered due to cultural differences at all?

R: No. No, I don't think so.

I: And what about challenges around affiliation? Because it was a consortium clearly individuals were coming with affiliations to their host organisations, and the intent of [XXX]. Were there any challenges in trying to mirror both per se? So instances where maybe you had an individual coming with particular paradigms in what they wanted to achieve by engaging with [XXX] at the consequence of their host organisations, but then engaging with [XXX] and perhaps the vehicle of [XXX] was slightly different from what they initially wanted to achieve because they were coming from a particular organisation. Did you encounter any such thing at all?

R: I'm not sure I follow. Can you repeat? What things? A mismatch between what?

I: A mismatch between perhaps the philosophical ethos of individuals' host organisations, so for instance an individual coming from a particular university, they might have a particular idea of collective intelligence or they might have a particular object which is something that their host institution supports, but then [XXX] as a project might have a different interpretation or objective. Was that ever an issue?

R: Yes, I see what you mean. Of course we encountered that. If you read the final project report you will find this aspect too. So one of the main problems we found was that our definition of collective intelligence was different, and collective intelligence technology was different from some of the partners we engaged with. Some of the people were writing to the open call and were expecting the collective intelligence tools to do something completely different. So I think that happened, and that's why it took all the time, even when we had to build surveys or we had to engage with people individually, we had created training material and also some part of the engagement was always going through our definition of collective intelligence, our definition of collective intelligence tools, detailed descriptions, in order to avoid this happening, so that people would then pursue collaboration only if they really were in line with the same understanding. So that happened, but we tried to solve it simply by making more transparent our definitions.

I: So the overall aim of the (unclear 1.03.36) project is to link up the global world by promoting many organisations and we want to do this by forming a global ring community and to mobilise some resource that would a global open access resource around responsible research. That's our overall aim. But in doing this, can you perhaps advise or warn us against any potential dangers that we should be guarding against in trying to achieve this objective?

R: Is your objective to create a network of people or a network of resources or funding? It's really complex for me to respond to that because I don't really know what you mean by network and again we discussed different interpretations and the importance of definitions. I may have a different definition of network from yours, so for me the most important thing would be to try and understand what network you want to build. What is this? Are you trying to bring people together? Which way?

I: What we want to do is to build a community of individuals (unclear 1.05.12) community of individuals, stakeholders or organisations, but to build a community of individuals who actually work around responsible research and innovation, but to do this by building a community globally not just a European

community – it has to be a global community. And also to create an open access database, something like your database now. This is the objective but we are not sure what it would look like because we're still going through the process of the research and by having the interviews and speaking to people then we can begin to have a sense of what the network should look like. Should it even be a network? Because we're not quite sure yes. And it's only by having these interviews with individuals who have carried out projects around responsible research, collective intelligence and the like that we can begin to get a sense of what that community should be like and what -

R: No, I understand and I think it's a very good way of doing it. I don't know. I think (unclear 1.06.16) that would be part of the results of your analysis, what is the definition of this network? But you just said you want to build a community. Well reflecting on my experience on [XXX], one thing I can tell you for certain is communities are not built, they emerge. This was one of the big misconceptions we had in [XXX] when we started. We believed that we would engage with community partners, that's what we called them. Well, as I told you before, then we discovered that of all these, 90% of those defining themselves as community partners, they were nothing more than a network, or even less, a list of names, under a label, which is even worse.

Communities are completely different. It's that thing that I was telling you before, (unclear 1.07.27) have common values, common objectives and they do things together on an everyday basis. So it's not just about the value and subscribing to the same principles, but it's also having a pragmatic goal which is the same, and then working towards it together. So a community, really, I struggle to believe can be created. A network can be created, a community really just emerges. One or more communities may emerge inside a network. But your objective is higher than building a simple network and if you really want to create a community then I think what is really, really important is first of all money [laughter], constant sources of funding. No, really it's true, because for example I think that (unclear 1.08.32) which was this funding strand, they really managed to create a community, it's impressive. It was just a funding brand and now they have built a community of people, it is surviving through funding (unclear 1.08.52).

So they really managed to do it but they managed to do it across eight years, because they were constant in the providing of funding, constant in the dissemination of activities, knowledge sharing, and they have a huge amount of investment down in that. And that's because in order for the network individual to even recognise the stuff that's working as a community, they needed to have common projects, doing things together, (unclear 1.09.33), one, two, three times. A community member would have to recognise themselves as (unclear 1.09.41), you would have project, project (unclear 1.09.43), some organisations say 'Okay, I can work with you, I'm not going to work anymore with you and you.' [laughter] This way of consolidating the relationship while working together needs money to happen. (unclear 1.10.02-1.10.08), well first of all they need (unclear 1.10.11) to set up an awful lot of money for building it, for facilitating it [laughs]. They need to give you more money, you need more money for more time. [laughter]

That's my understanding, because you have an incredibly nice and positive goal. I'm sure you will achieve a network, I'm sure you will achieve a database or resources. I think a previous RRI project already did that, like (unclear 1.10.59), they have a database of resources and they have a big network, hundreds of people. Did they manage to create a community, self-sustaining community, like (unclear 1.11.09) did? I'm not sure. You have a very relevant project, you didn't even know each other.

So I don't know. I think moving from a network of individuals to a community is a very, very hard objective that you are setting yourself to reach. [laughs] It's very hard.

I: Yes, I recognise that it's difficult but how would you advise that we go about achieving that sense of community, so moving from engagement to building a community? What kind of steps would you advocate that we take in trying to achieve that? Are there any points you can give us?

R: Give people resources, give people responsibility and give people recognition and exposure, and keep repeating this for a long time. [laughter] That's what I do. No really [laughs], why are you laughing? Does it look a little bit stupid, what I said?

I: No, no. Hello?

R: Hello?

I: Yes I can hear you clearly. I was going to ask you to qualify the bit where you said give people recognition.

R: Yes.

I: So in giving them recognition, I'm not quite sure how we would do that. Would it be recognising their contributions to building the community? Would it be recognising their outputs? I'm not quite sure how the mechanical side to building the community...

R: You ([unclear 1.13.12](#)) from the people and the people you want to create, so if you want the community to have researchers in it, researchers will respond to different type of recognition. If you have a community organisation in it and you want to have them in the community, then they understand different things for recognition. So I think you need a variety of recognition mechanics and you need to be creative in how you deliver it and the best way would be to go and ask the representative of the people you want in the community 'What would be the drive, motivators and recognition for you?' And then you just create an activity for that.

The way of enacting it ([unclear 1.14.08](#)). It could be from digital vouchers to money to visibility inside public events, a media feature, a newspaper, in a journal, a ([unclear 1.14.25](#)), a radio interview, it could be anything really, a million things, it could be ([unclear 1.14.33](#)). But the important thing is really that I believe in order to create really that community sense, you have to give people resources otherwise people don't do things because we are all busy and we are all doing a million things, you're ([unclear 1.14.57](#)) into something new, so you need to give them resources. Then you need to give them responsibility and ownership because they don't say and they don't feel part of a community until they feel that they own a bit of it, then they are responsible for it and they feel they have a sense of responsibility, so you need to give them that I think. And then they need to be practically involved in some activity for which you have given them responsibility and resources. And if they achieve, in many different ways, you have to celebrate their success because this is how you really motivate them to stay and to feel part of that. So to me, these are ([recording inaudible 1.15.55](#)) for developing the sense of community, that's why I said ([unclear 1.16.00-1.16.01](#)). [laughs]e

I: Fantastic.

R: Resources, responsibility and whatever, I don't remember anymore. But I really think these things are important and the celebration and visibility are a very big part of it. I

think that the role that is needed about being so good at disseminating [XXX]'s achievements was really important, both for us to keep us going, to enable us to have the visibility that was enough to then have the sustainability part, and also to develop a sense of pride in being part of the project. So I think these are really important values if you want to go about facilitating the emergence of a community, like the RRI network.

I: Fantastic, thank you very much for qualifying that. And thank you for sharing your experience and particularly for taking the time with the interview because I recognise it was a very difficult interview for you because obviously we are trying to look at a network and we ended up talking about the project in retrospect, so thank you very much for the time. But before we end I just wondered if there was anything else you would like to share your thoughts about, if there are any things you would like to qualify or you would like to (unclear 1.17.45) any further comments or remarks at all?

R: No, I think I'm okay. I think we covered everything that occurs to me at the moment. I just wish you a lot of luck and I hope that was useful in some way.

I: Yes, it was very useful and it was a real delight and pleasure to chat with you and hear about your range of experiences. So it was very much appreciated and very well received. But just quickly, at the end of the interviews, once we have a draft report, we will be sharing that with the individuals who have contributed to the interviews and so we'll be happy to share that with you once we have that.

R: Yes, that would be really nice, thank you very much. I would like that.

I: No worries. Again it was a pleasure to have spoken to you and thank you for your time, it's very much appreciated once again.

R: Yes, it was my pleasure (unclear 1.18.49) and good luck for your project. It looks a very, very appreciative and nice one so good luck.

I: Thank you very much and take care and have a good evening.

R: Bye-bye.

I: Bye.

R: You too, bye.

(End of recording)